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Editorial Message

A very warm welcome to you all!

I am happy to extend my warm greetings to you all and congratulate our whole team of Journal of Applied Dental and Medical Sciences for the successful launch of inaugural first issue Apr-June 2015 vol. 1 issue 1. Journal will be published online 4 times a year and equipped with facility of fast manuscript reviewing system and Pre-Publishing Communication With Authors To Know Their Manuscript Status Time To Time.

Journal has been graced with the Presence of esteemed Advisory Board Members and I am sure that their valuable guidance and support will always be a lifeline for the successful working of the Journal.

My sincere thanks to Editorial Board Members for their continuous suggestions and contributions to complete the editing of First Issue.

Being a Peer review journal, manuscript undergoes through blind review from our review board members who are actually the pillars of Journal. So I thank to all review members for their sincere reviews and giving precious time to review papers.

I am inviting colleagues from both Medical and Dental fraternity to join and help us to increase awareness of research work culture in India and make each other updated and acknowledged about the newer advances in both fields.

Our Journal would not have been materialized without efforts of our Journal's Associate Editor Dr. Shashi Bhushan Gupta and Consultant Editor Dr. Madhvi Singh.

I end my writing with the famous quote from a very famous researcher:

"Imagination is the highest form of research"

..... Albert Einstein

Regards

Dr. Manish Goutam

Editor-in-chief